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THE INCIDENCE OF MALIGNANT NEOPLASMS ON THE TERRITORY OF THE REPUBLIC OF BELARUS. CURRENT TRENDS

T.I. Zimatkina,

Ph.D., Associate Professor

A.S. Aleksandrovich,

Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor

I. A. Aleksandrovich,

Grodno State Medical University,

Grodno

Annotation: The trends in mortality and morbidity of the population of the Republic of Belarus in malignant neoplasms of various localization are analyzed, the ratio of two indicators in different localization of malignant neoplasms and in dynamics is analyzed. As a result of the conducted studies, the problem of the growth of oncological pathology in recent decades has been revealed, which is explained by an increase in the average annual increase in cancer cases.

Keywords: mortality, morbidity, neoplasms

ЗАБОЛЕВАЕМОСТЬ ЗЛОКАЧЕСТВЕННЫМИ НОВООБРАЗОВАНИЯМИ НА ТЕРРИТОРИИ РЕСПУБЛИКИ БЕЛАРУСЬ. СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ

Т.И. Зиматкина,

к.б.н., доц.

А.С. Александрович,

к.м.н., доц.

И.А. Александрович,

Гродненский государственный медицинский университет,

г. Гродно

Аннотация: Проанализированы тенденции в смертности и заболеваемости населения Республики Беларусь при злокачественных новообразованиях различной локализации, проведен анализ соотношения двух показателей при различных локализациях злокачественных новообразований и в динамике. В результате проведенных исследований выявлена проблема роста онкологической патологии в последние десятилетия, что объясняется увеличением показателя среднегодового прироста случаев онкозаболеваемости.

Keywords: смертность, заболеваемость, новообразования

Relevance. The International Agency for Research on Cancer annually registers more than 12 million new cases of cancer and about 6.2 million deaths from it. The annual rate of increase in the incidence of malignant neoplasms (ZN) is approximately 2 %, which exceeds the growth of the world population by 0.3-0.5 %.

The forecast of the experts of the World Health Organization is disappointing: cancer incidence worldwide will increase to 24 million cases by 2050, and mortality to 16 million annually registered cases.

For many years in the countries of the European region, as well as in the Republic of Belarus, oncological pathology ranks second in the structure of all causes of death after diseases of the circulatory system and significantly affects the average life expectancy of the population.

According to 2018 data, the most common oncological diseases in the world are: lung, breast and bowel cancer. The analysis of the incidence of malignant neoplasms is necessary for health protection, the development of preventive measures, the solution of strategic and tactical tasks of health management. To date, much has already been done to understand the problem as a whole, a huge amount of material has been accumulated, the systematization and generalization of which ultimately allows us to answer many questions related to the etiology and pathogenesis of cancer.

Reducing morbidity and mortality from malignant neoplasms is one of the most urgent problems facing medical science and healthcare at the present time. According to the World Health Organization and the International Agency for Research on Cancer, malignant neoplasms are a modern global problem.

The purpose of the study. To analyze trends in mortality and morbidity of the population of the Republic of Belarus in malignant neoplasms of various localization, to analyze the ratio of two indicators in different localization of malignant neoplasms and in dynamics.

Material and methods of research. In the work, using epidemiological and comparative evaluation methods, official statistical data on the health status of the population of the Republic of Belarus, as well as literature data on morbidity and mortality from malignant neoplasms were studied.

Results and their discussion. In the Republic of Belarus for the period from 1995 to 2018, an increase in primary morbidity was registered in the class of "Neoplasms": 296.1 cases per 100 thousand population in 1995, 328.7 – in 2000, 367.2 – in 2005, 442.9 – in 2010, 513.4 – in 2015, 554.5 – in 2018. that is, for 23 years, this indicator has grown by 87.3%. In the period from 1995 to 2005, the average annual increase in morbidity was 7.11; from 2005 to 2015 – 14.62; from 2015 to 2018 – 13.7. On the territory of the Republic of Belarus, there is an increase in this pathology in the period from 1995 to 2018. on average by 3.8 % (11.2 cases per 100 thousand population) per year.

With the growth of cancer incidence in the Republic of Belarus at such a rate in the future, the number of cases will double in 15 years, which will not only significantly increase the burden on the healthcare system of the republic, but also entail significant socio-economic consequences. According to official statistics, more than 40 thousand patients have been registered annually in our country since 2011, and since 2017 – more than 50 thousand patients with a diagnosis of "malignant neoplasm" for the first time in their lives, which is about 0.5 % of the country's population [1, 4].

The incidence of men with ZN of all localizations is generally higher than that of women. It should be noted that the greatest increase in morbidity is observed at the age of 60 and older, and in 2018 amounted to 1719 cases per 100 thousand people of the population.

The structure of cancer incidence in men has changed over the period from 2000 to 2010. In 2000, lung cancer was in the first place, stomach cancer in the second and colon cancer in the third; in 2010, respectively, lung cancer, prostate cancer and non-melanoma skin cancer. In 2018 and 2019, men most often have prostate cancer, lung cancer and colorectal cancer.

The structure of cancer incidence in women has not changed significantly over the same period. Among women in 2000, the first three positions were occupied by: breast, skin and stomach cancer. The leading positions in women in 2010 were occupied by skin cancer (19.8 %), breast cancer (17.6 %), uterine body (7.7 %), followed by stomach cancer (6.1 %). In 2018 and 2019, breast cancer is leading, followed by colorectal cancer and uterine cancer. [1, 2, 4].

In Belarus, 6-9 % of detected cases of oncological diseases annually are primary multiple tumors, of which every fifth case is the localization of tumors in two or more organs at the same time, which indicates an increase in cases of polyneoplasia. According to data for 2010, the main part in their structure (62.1 %) are cases of non-melanoma skin cancer (17.7 % of all detected cases of skin cancer). Primary multiple tumors in 10.1 % of the detected cases were lip tumors, 4 % – esophagus, 2.6 % – stomach, 7.9 % – colon, 5.7 % – kidney, 2.7 % – thyroid gland. The most rapid increase in the incidence of prostate cancer and non-melanoma skin cancer [2, 3].

Mortality from oncological pathology in Belarus remains high: in 1995 – 188.1 cases per 100 thousand population, in 2000 – 194.3; in 2005 – 188.5; in 2010 – 191.6; in 2015 – 183.9 and in 2018 – 196.0. From 1995 to 2018, the total mortality rate increased by 4.2 % has remained relatively stable in the last decade, with a tendency to a slight decrease. Moreover, the mortality rate among the rural population suffering from cancer is significantly higher than that of the urban population. Thus, the ratio correlates the mortality of urban and rural population per 100 thousand. The number of people was 167.2 and 245.5 in 1995; 181.5 and 232.4 in 2010; 175.9 and 223.4 in 2015; 184.4 and 250.1 in 2018.

For the period from 1995 to 2018, lung cancer took the first place in mortality among all localities of ZN (as of 2010, 3280 people). The second and third places were taken by stomach cancer and colorectal cancer (2290 and 2259 people). This is followed by breast cancer (1,220 people) and prostate cancer (855 people). In 2017, mortality from lung cancer comes out on top (3,112 people), colorectal cancer is in second place (2,418 people), stomach cancer is in third place (1,860 people) [3, 4].

Conclusions. As a result of the conducted research, the problem of the growth of oncological pathology in recent decades has been revealed. This is due to an increase in the average annual increase in cancer cases.

The incidence of men with ZN of all localizations in general was always higher than that of women.

During the analyzed period, the Republic of Belarus has seen the greatest increase in the incidence of skin, breast and prostate cancer, and the largest number of deaths is recorded from lung cancer.

The mortality rate of the rural population from year to year exceeds the number of deaths from malignant neoplasms in the urban population.

The revealed difference in the growth rates of oncological morbidity and mortality over a 23-year period (from 1995 to 2018, the incidence increased by 87.3 %, and mortality increased by only 4.2 %, and remained at a relatively unchanged level for a decade) indicates the effectiveness of providing medical care to oncological patients and the need to reduce the level and growth rates morbidity of ZN of the population of Belarus.

Given the high effectiveness of modern preventive work, it is necessary to focus efforts on primary and secondary prevention of this pathology.

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